

Decomposition of Diethyldithiocarbamic Acid

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When sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (NaDDC) is titrated against HCl, HClO₄ or HAs, two equivalents of the acid are consumed per mole of NaDDC¹. Alternatively², it has been suggested that the acid is a monobasic one and the second equivalent of the acid is utilized in decomposing the acid into carbon disulphide and diethylamine as follows:

The stability of NaDDC in presence of acid has been studied by various workers^{3,4,5} and it is concluded that the stability increases in a marked manner with increase in pH. The decomposition of dithiocarbamate by addition of a proton is explained⁶ by the following reactions:

Goksyor⁷ titrated sodium dimethyldithiocarbamate (NaDMDT) with HCl. He found that two equivalents of the acid were required to reach the end point. When the solution was back titrated afterwards, it behaved as a strong acid-base system. He concluded that HDMDT decomposes completely into CS₂ and dimethylaminehydrochloride. It may be remarked that NaDMDT is less stable than NaDDC.

From the above it is reasonable to accept that the acid corresponding to NaDDC which is more stable than NaDMDT may be stable at least above pH 6. The initial pH of 0.025 M NaDDC is about 9. On addition of an acid, pH gradually drops and the end point is obtained when two equivalents of the acid are consumed. This is taken to assume that the corresponding acid is a dibasic one. To prevent the decomposition of the acid, NaDDC was titrated against a still weaker acid like KH₂PO₄. The end point was obtained by plotting the graph of dpH/dV against V. Even when an excess of the acid is added the pH

1. Soni and Trivedi, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 37, 349.
2. Greenlee *et al.*, Preprint 71, session I of Nuclear Engineering and Science Conference, Chicago, March, 17-21, 1958.
3. Bode, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1954, 142, 414.
4. Lopatecki and Newton, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1952, 30, 131.
5. Hallaway, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1959, 36, 538; vide, Thorn and Ludwig, 'The dithiocarbamates and related compounds', Elsevier Publishing Co. N. Y. 1962, p.50.
6. Zuman and Zahradnik, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1957, 268, 135.
7. Goksyor, *Physiologia Plantarum*, 1955, 8, 737.

does not go below 6.5. This supports the view that the acid is a dibasic one and is stable at pH 6.5, and above.

When NaDDC is titrated against an acid and the titration is stopped just when the two equivalents of the acid are added the solution gives yellow or yellowish brown colour of copper diethyldithiocarbamate complex with cupric ions. On the other hand, the absence of the formation of yellow or yellowish brown colour indicates the decomposition of dithiocarbamate ions. Table below gives some of the selected observations. The acid was mixed with NaDDC and was kept for 48 hours. Subsequently, when cupric sulphate was added the yellow colour was obtained. This also confirms the stability of dithiocarbamate ions. If the pH is carefully maintained, the dibasic acid is stable.

TABLE I

No. ml. and Molarity of NaDDC	ml. and Normality of the acid	Equivalents of the acid added	pH	Colour with cupric ions
1. 6.2ml. of 0.1M	50 ml. of 0.0248N HClO_4	Two	7.4	Yellow
2. 2.5ml. of 0.1M	50 ml. of 0.01N HAc	Two	7.5	Brownish yellow
3. 5.0 ml. of 0.05 M	50 ml. of 0.01N HAc	Two	7.4	Yellow
4. 50 ml. of 0.025M	2.02ml. of 1.24N HClO_4	Two	7.3	Yellow

The stability of diethyldithiocarbamic acid was also studied by its inhibition capacity for the corrosion of copper. The corrosion of copper was studied in buffers of different pH with and without NaDDC. It was found that NaDDC acts as an excellent inhibitor for the corrosion of copper above pH 5.1. When NaDDC is titrated against HClO_4 , HCl and HAc, the jump occurs at about pH equal to 7 and hence, it is reasonable to assume the stability of the dibasic diethyldithiocarbamic acid.

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